

PROCEDIA OF PHILOSOPHICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

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1st International Conference on
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Physical Training as an Important Component of Pre-Conscription Military Training of Young People

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Abstract. This article is intended for students (cadets) of the Faculty of Military Training and Physical Education of higher educational institutions, as well as for teachers on the subject of pre-conscription military training. The purpose of the article: to provide information about physical training as an important component of pre-conscription military training of young people.

Key words: adaptation, preparation, program, staff, system, complex.

Physical training is an integral part of the training of pre-conscription youth, aimed primarily at strengthening the organs and systems of the body, increasing their functional capabilities, developing motor qualities (strength, speed, endurance, flexibility, dexterity) with simultaneous improvement of the ability to coordinate movements, show strong-willed qualities, improve the technique of performing exercises.

Physical training consists of two parts:

- ✓ general physical training (GPhT);
- ✓ Special physical training (SPhT).

General physical training (GPhT) is a mandatory part of the pre-conscription training.

- ✓ общая физическая подготовка (ОФП);
- ✓ специальная физическая подготовка (СФП).

Общая физическая подготовка (ОФП) является обязательной составной частью подготовки допризывника.

Общая физическая подготовка

Under the influence of general physical training, the health of young people is strengthened, the ability to work increases, the adaptive reactions of the body to loads of different

directions and the ability to tolerate them improve, the level of motor qualities increases. While working with pre-conscription youth, you can focus on the exemplary general physical training program, which contains the main groups of exercises. Guided by it, you can create your own general physical training program, which will be based on general developmental exercises without objects and with objects, in pairs, on gymnastic equipment.

The main goal - is to increase working capacity and increase muscle mass.

Tasks:

- a) increasing the ability to exercise strength;
- b) increased strength endurance;
- c) improvement of muscle elasticity and mobility in joints;
- d) correction of defects of physique and bearing.

Tools. Exercises with a barbell, kettlebells and other loads (bench press, push, jerk, squats, bends, turns, etc.). Are performed until significant muscle fatigue (until the correctness of movements is violated) in 1-3 approaches with a rest interval of 2-5 minutes. The intensity of the exercise is 50-70% of the maximum. These exercises are included in the main classes 3 times a week.

Exercises aimed at overcoming one's own body weight (push-ups lying down, pulling up on a crossbar, squatting on one leg with a "pistol", etc.). The same is true on gymnastic equipment (gymnastic wall, gymnastic bench, crossbar), tree branches. Exercises are performed "to failure" in 1-3 sets with a rest interval of 1-3 minutes.

Jumping exercises with forward movement (from foot to foot, on one leg, on two legs) are performed "to failure". They are repeated 1-2 times with a rest interval of 1-3 minutes and are included in the main classes 2-3 times a week.

The main goal - is to develop the ability to show the force of pushing with your feet (foot) in motion or during a jump from a place.

Tasks:

- a) education of the will to show maximum effort;
- b) increasing the ability to concentrate attention and effort;
- c) increasing the speed of movements.

Tools. Barbell exercises — squats with gradual weight gain, jumping with weights, etc. are performed several times in 2-3 sets. The rest interval is 2-3 minutes. They are included in the main classes 2 times a week.

The same exercises with a barbell, the intensity of performance is accelerated, the rest interval is increased. They are included in the main classes 2 times a week.

Isometric (static) exercises (push-ups, pull-ups, twists, etc.). Are performed once, with maximum tension for 6-8 seconds, in 2-4 sets at intervals of 1-2 minutes. They are included in the main classes 2 times a week.

Exercises with jumps with a subject orientation (to reach out to a suspended object, jump

from a place to a gymnastic bench, jump over an obstacle, overcome a 30 m segment with jumps in the shortest time or with the least number of jumps, etc.). The intensity is maximum. They are included in the main classes 2 times a week.

Throwing projectiles (a stuffed ball, a grenade, a core, a stone, etc.) at a target, the distance to which is gradually increasing. The intensity is maximum. Perform 20-30 throws in class 2 times a week.

The main goal - is to increase the overall speed of movements.

Tasks:

- a) improved coordination of movements;
- b) increased dexterity;
- c) increase of general endurance.

Tools. General developmental exercises, Each exercise is performed with the greatest possible speed. A set of 4-5 exercises is performed in 2-3 sets in series of 10 s . They are held in 3-4 main classes.

Running 20-50 m on the move, from the start, relay, with overcoming obstacles and handicap. It is performed several times at intervals of 2-3 minutes.

Sports and outdoor games (basketball, volleyball, football on a reduced field, wrestling for the ball, etc.). Play by the rules. The game time can be shortened. Games are held as a special lesson or in the main lesson instead of a warm-up or at the end of the lesson.

The main goal - is to develop general endurance.

Tasks:

- a) education of the will, adaptation to the transfer of loads;
- b) strengthening of muscles, joints and ligaments;
- c) developing the ability to relax.

Tools. Running at a steady pace at a heart rate (heart rate) of 130-150 beats / min during the main class 2 times a week with a gradual increase in running time, starting from 10-15 minutes. Running can be replaced by skiing, cycling, working on an exercise bike, etc.

General developmental exercises with objects (dumbbells, jump ropes, stuffed ball, stick, etc.) and without them. Continuous performance of a set of exercises by the current and circular method with an average intensity for 5-15 minutes is included in the main classes 3 times a week after the warm-up.

Running is performed, if possible, non-stop with low and medium intensity for 5-15 minutes, is included in the warm-up during the main classes.

Swimming (30-60 min)

The main goal - is to develop overall flexibility and coordination.

Tasks:

- a) increased muscle elasticity;

b) improved coordination of movements.

Tools: Exercises with a large amplitude in all joints and in all directions (bends, turns, somersaults, bending, swinging, etc.) on projectiles, with and without objects. Each exercise is performed in the form of a series with 4-6 repetitions with an increasingly increasing amplitude, 2-3 series with rest intervals of 10-20 seconds. All exercises are given 8-10 minutes.

The main goal - is to further improve the coordination of movements and the development of dexterity.

Task:

- a) development of the ability to manifest "explosive" force;
- b) education of courage and determination;
- c) development of flexibility;
- d) increased muscle elasticity;
- e) strengthening of muscles.

Tools. Acrobatic exercises (somersaults, flips, flips, etc.). Exercises on a flip board and trampoline. Perform several times, spending 15-25 minutes on all exercises together with rest intervals. Include in the main classes once a week.

Exercises on gymnastic equipment (support jumps, swings, flips, lifts, etc. on the bars and crossbar). Perform repeatedly with rest intervals of 1-2 minutes, spending 15-30 minutes on all exercises. Include in the main classes 3 times a week.

It is recommended to use the class time more effectively. In particular, during rest, you can perform exercises that require less effort (for example, squeezing a tennis ball with a brush) or another orientation (for example, practicing the technique of a mastered movement or learning a new one).

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